

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

IMPORTANCE OF USING MNEMONICS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract

Modern educational system inquires remembering enormous amounts of information. Very often students experience inability to remember all of it and even start disliking a subject. Not every child knows how to learn facts effectively, therefore, modern educational system should include this knowledge in a lesson curriculum. There are a number of methods, which can make the process of learning easier and help the learners to remember information better and efficiently, keeping it way longer. Mnemonics can be seen as one of those method. The focus of this paper is to address how important mnemonic is for modern educational system and for foreign language teaching in particular.

Keywords: Mnemonics, Mnemonic method, modern teaching approaches, ELT, foreign language teaching

Introduction

The aim of this paper is to explore why mnemonic method is important for modern English teaching. The authors will focus on history of mnemonic and its development, providing some models of possible usage of different methods on English lessons and identifying their role in developing memory skills. The article consists of five parts, with each part devoted to different aspects of development of mnemonics and examples.

Discussion

The definition of mnemonic. A mnemonic device, or memory device, is any learning technique that helps person to remember information. Mnemonic tools are those things which person already knows and can use as an association to code new knowledge [4]. Different mnemonic methods allow to make abstract definitions, which can be difficult to remember, more objective and meaningful.

The history of mnemonics. According to legend, first author of mnemonic system was Simonides, Ancient Greek poet (Simonides of Ceos; Greek: Σιμωνίδης ὁ Κεῖος; c. 556–468 BC). He managed to name every victim on the Scopas's feast remembering where the person was sitting. It has led to the appearance of first law of memorizing using the place of objects. Simonides later invented the "memory palace", a mnemonic system used to remember things placing them into rooms of the palace. Mnemonic methods were widely used by many philosophers such as Aristotle, Pythagoras, Socrates and others. The rise of popularity of mnemonics occurred in the middle ages. At this time, the

list of mnemonic literature has expanded significantly. Mnemonic was honoured by many great people of that time. There is a well-known interest in the mnemonics of Giordano Bruno, Shakespeare, Kant, Thomas Aquinas, and many others. So, in the well-known Shakespeare's globe theatre, many actors used sophisticated mnemonic systems in their performances. The Shakespeare theatre was even called the "theatre of Memory". Mnemonic system is still developing. Nowadays more and more technics are appearing. Many of them are integrated into studying process [9].

The effects of mnemonic on remembering information. Great number of experiments on the effect of using mnemonic was conducted. ('*Mnemonic facilitation of learning disabled students' memory for expository prose*', '*Comparative effectiveness of a mnemonic-use approach vs. self-study to interpret a lateral chest X-ray*' etc). Many of them proved the effectiveness of using mnemonic in studying process. Thus, in the experimental research in Senior High School 01 of Punggur (2018/2019) the researchers investigated the English vocabulary of the students of tenth grade. Students were given pre-test and post-test to compare the results. The average result of the group was 55 scores. After this test researchers taught the students different mnemonic technics which then were used for memorizing words. On the post-test the group has shown better results with an average score 80,5. This experiment has shown that mnemonic technics definitely help in learning process as students from Punggur remembered

more words after using that method in comparison to their previous results.

Researchers also claim that the students were much more involved in the learning process “because it included visual capability and creativity among students so that they might take part better during learning process” [3].

The importance of using mnemonics in teaching English. Using mnemonics increases students` interest. When teacher gives vivid associations to remember words or grammar structures, learners are more interested in subject than if teacher would ask them to learn the material by heart [7]. Such method also improves student`s imagination. For instance, when using vocabulary, a teacher can ask learners to create association to remember the word. Often students get stuck on some topics because they simply cannot remember big amounts of information. Using mnemonics on English lessons can give students a chance to memorize information quicker which can help a teacher to finish the course faster.

Results

The authors have discussed what mnemonic method is and why it is important for learning and teaching process. To show how exactly this method may be used, some mnemonic technics can be introduced below.

Acronyms

This is “an abbreviation consisting of the first letters of each word in the name of something, pronounced as a word” (Cambridge Dictionary). Here are some examples of such strategy:

1. Remembering colours of the rainbow

Red

Orange

Yellow

Green

Blue

Indigo

Violet

First letters of every colour make the acronym “ROYGBIV”.

2. Memorizing the 7 coordinating conjunctions in English:

For

And

Nor

But

Or

Yet

So

Acronym of these words will be “FANBOYS”

Acronyms help students to remember big amounts of information as it is much easier to remember short words than all the material they have to learn. However, students must be taught how to use acronyms properly. Teachers need to explain that these words must be decoded in order not to get answer “ROYGBIV” on question about colours of rainbow.

Keyword Method

Another popular mnemonic method is keyword method. It helps to memorize abstract notions linking them with real objects. It is important to say that objects

in this mnemonic picture must interact, otherwise, it will be a bad mnemonic [4].

For instance, student needs to remember the word “transient” (lasting for only a short time). This word is close to pronunciation of “train – see – ant”. Student can imagine that train goes on high speed and sees the ant who can die, so life of insect lasts for a short time.

Teachers should remember that pronunciation of learnt words often is not close to its spelling. Therefore, work on orthography must be performed.

Image Mnemonic

This method can be used for memorizing objects. Images can be both real (printed) or imaginary [1]. For instance, student needs to remember that with the word “chocolate” we use “bar”. So, the imaginary picture of it can be a little boy sitting in bar and eating chocolate because he is not allowed to drink alcohol. This technic helps to build vivid images in student`s mind, thus, allowing him/her to remember information better. Printed images can also be used for remembering information. This is one of types of using flashcards. Usually, flashcards consist of the word on one side and its definition on the other side. In comparison, mnemonic flashcards can reflect the image only. In its turn, teacher should explain association between the word and the picture before testing students.

Conclusion

Students often have problems with memorizing information, especially if they do not like the subject or it seems too difficult for them. Proved effectiveness of mnemonic technics allows students to use them in learning process. Moreover, either teachers are recommended to use mnemonic on lessons to increase learner`s interest in subject and allow them to remember more information.

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DEVELOPMENT OF COGNITIVE-COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the problem of development of cognitive communicative competence of high school students in teaching foreign language. In this article the approaches of the formation of this competence in FLT by means of internet resources will be considered as the first step of training highly- qualified future specialists who will meet all the requirements of modern society, at the same time modernizing education system of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

Keywords: cognitive - communicative competence, modernization, high school, foreign language teaching, Internet resources.

Nowadays in connection with modern tendencies in the development of education system of Kazakhstan, there is a need for specialists who are able to work and compete in international labour market, and who have intercultural communicative competencies, including cognitive- communicative competence. So, according to this education system of the Republic of Kazakhstan joined the Bologna process which gave us an opportunity to enter the European system of education.

The signing of the Bologna Agreement by Kazakhstan, under which a single European educational space is being created, was an inevitable consequence and an indispensable condition for the implementation of the transformations taking place in our country in general and in the system of foreign language education in particular. Changing socio-cultural conditions, the developing mobility and openness of society, the need for the convertibility of Kazakhstani diplomas make it necessary to take into account global trends in reforming the Kazakhstani educational system.

As the analysis of works devoted to the problems of the need for the formation of cognitive-communicative competence has shown, this concept traditionally considered in parallel rather than in interconnection.

Cognition and communication are recognized as two main functions of the human language. Initially in the linguistic tradition the priority role was assigned to the communicative function of a language, then in recent decades, marked by the development of the cognitive science, the study of language is viewed as the active process of learning, cognition, mental activity of human consciousness.

According to S.S.Kunanbayeva, one of the priority directions of modernization of education in our country is the idea of competence-based education. The competence-based approach is the basis for achieving a new quality of education. It determines the direction of changes in the educational process. The study of the competence-based approach in education was carried out by such authors as S.S.Kunanbaeva, D.N.Kulibaeva, D.B.Elkonin, I.A.Zimnyaya, A.V.Khutorsky, E.F. Zeer, J. Raven and others.[1]

The fundamental goal of foreign language education is the formation of the foreign language communicative competence. [2]

Communicative competence is the ability to communicate effectively and efficiently. Communicative competence is a complex formation that includes various structural components. There are many approaches to considering the structure of communicative competence. Communicative competence was first mentioned by Naum Chomsky in 1965, in his writings he draws the line between linguistic and pragmatic competence. Issues related to the definition and essence of the development and formation of the cognitive competence of students were considered in the works of Yu.V. Borisova, A.B. Burovoy, V.I. Ginetsinsky, I.V. Grebenev, B.K. Elmanova, H.B. Kuzmina, C.B. Tretyakova, A.P. Kharina, etc. [3]

Based on the theoretical basis of the development of cognitive-communicative competence of high school students we need to create a model. But first of all there should be particular approaches we will create our model based on. Methodological approaches to